

Different Initial Assumptions for Statistical and Quantum

Mechanics?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. and S.P.N. Messina Nov. 27, 2019

Statistical mechanics seems to be based on the idea of distributing a fixed amount of energy among a number of particles. (Usually this number is very large.) Alternatively, one may think of a single particle changing its state (e.g. momentum) during many time intervals. In both cases, one takes an average of the energy, but this means one needs weights for each single particle state. These weights seem to be based on the idea that each 'vector' of states has the same probability of occurrence. Thus, if one has N particles and an energy eN , one vector involves one particle having eN and the rest 0. Many vectors, however, may be created with N particles having energy near e . Thus, the weight for a single particle to have energy e is much higher than for it to have energy E . The weight is ultimately taken to be the Boltzmann factor.

In quantum mechanics, it seems a very different assumption is made. Unlike classical physics where one follows a particle in space and time, knowing its acceleration, position and velocity at each x , in quantum mechanics, collisions with the potential seem to be granular, and the main assumption seems to be that a quantum particle may be in any momentum plane wave state at a given time. Like statistical mechanics, there is a set of weights, but one no longer uses the scenario of distributing energy among different states to determine these weights. Instead, the weights are obtained by noting that a quantum average at a point x is taken using $f_p \exp(ipx) / (\text{Sum over } f_p \exp(ipx))$. The weights must ensure that:

$$-1/2m (\text{Sum over } p \ p^2/2m f_p \exp(ipx)) / (\text{Sum over } f_p \exp(ipx)) = E - V(x) \text{ at each } x \text{ point.}$$

Thus, the plane wave behavior of quantum particles becomes a dominant factor. For the case of $V(x)=0$, the plane wave nature of the possible single particle momentum states leads to an overall $(\text{Sum over } f_p \exp(ipx))$ which has the appearance to two plane waves. This is very different from the classical statistical mechanical case.

In this note, we attempt to examine the difference of these two statistical theories, and understand why in one case, the ground state of an oscillator, the two become the same.

Classical Statistical Mechanics

In classical statistical mechanics, one deals with micro-canonical, canonical and grand canonical distributions in addition to maximizing $-\text{Sum over } n \ P_n \ln(P_n) + b$ constraint where P_n is the probability of a state and b a constant. These various approaches are linked more or less to the Boltzmann factor $\exp(-e/T)$ where e =energy which is often $p^2/2m + V(r)$. In statistical mechanical textbooks, however, it is argued that the underlying idea of statistical mechanics is the equality of the weight of every possible state which may exist, subject to a set of constraints. Thus, given N particles and a total energy E , one may write 'vectors' which include N particles. Each vector

carries the same weight of 1. The energies of the particles in a vector must add to E. If a particle may only have kinetic energy, then:

$p_1^2/2m + p_2^2/2m + p_3^2/2m + \dots = E$ for a particular vector. Not all N particles need a nonzero momentum in a given vector.

One particle may have energy E, and the rest zero. Other scenarios include single particle energies approximately equal to E/N. One may then determine the weight for a specific single particle energy by counting the number of times this energy appears in the vectors. This should lead to a result very similar to the Boltzmann factor, or the factor itself in certain limits.

Alternatively, one may consider one particle and N time intervals and repeat the above analysis.

Quantum Mechanics Without a Potential

Consider a quantum particle in a box with an infinite potential at the walls, but no potential inside. There is only one particle, so one may consider N time intervals for one particle, as in the classical statistical case. Furthermore, during each time interval, a quantum particle may be in a different momentum state (plane wave state) like in classical statistical mechanics. Each momentum state has a kinetic energy of $p^2/2m$. Thus at first, it seems one has the same conditions of classical statistical mechanics, but this is not the case.

First of all, the average kinetic energy in quantum mechanics is not calculated by summing $p^2/2m$, rather it is given by:

$$\text{KE average at } x = (\text{Sum over } p \quad p^2/2m \text{ } f_p \exp(ipx)) / (\text{Sum over } p \text{ } f_p \exp(ipx)) \quad ((1))$$

Nevertheless, one may set x to a particular value, say $x=0$, and then essentially obtain a classical statistical mechanical average. One might then think that vectors may be created like in the classical mechanical case to obtain f_p . This is not the case. Thus, something very different must occur in quantum mechanics.

It seems that quantum mechanics is strongly based on the idea of the plane wave $\exp(ipx)$, which may be thought of as a two channel system i.e. $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ which are linked in a periodic fashion. For a quantum particle in a box with its center at $x=0$, a particle might be in any p plane wave momentum state with a weight f_p . Thus, if the total energy of the system is E, then at $x=0$:

$$E = (\text{Sum over } p \text{ } p^2/2m \text{ } f_p) / (\text{Sum over } p \text{ } f_p) \quad ((2))$$

The same result, however, must follow if one replaces f_p in ((2)) with $f_p \exp(ipx)$. This is a very different condition from that of classical statistical mechanics.

In quantum mechanics, a particle may be found in a particular p state or $\exp(ipx)$. If different p states are available, the average should be:

$$\text{Sum over } p \text{ } (\cos(px)f_p) + i \text{ Sum over } p \text{ } (\sin(px)f_p) \quad ((3))$$

One may set x equal to zero in ((3)) and obtain ((2)). This would seem to indicate one has a classical statistical mechanical situation. The idea, however, seems to be that

the average kinetic energy associated with ((3)) cannot change as one changes x even though the value of ((3)) changes from x_1 to x_2 . It also changes for the plane wave $\exp(ipx)$ although the momentum p and kinetic energy $p^2/2m$ do not change. Thus, for no potential present in the interior of the box, quantum mechanics seems to dictate that the f_p 's must be such that the average kinetic energy from ((3)) is the same at each x . This condition may be written as:

$$\left(\sum_p \frac{p^2}{2m} f_p \exp(ipx) \right) / \left(\sum_p f_p \exp(ipx) \right) = E \quad ((4))$$

For classical statistical mechanics with no potential there is no restriction due to x . In quantum mechanics there is, in fact, this condition is strong enough to dictate the values of f_p as ((4)) may be rewritten as a differential equation:

$$-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W = E W \quad \text{where } W = \sum_p f_p \exp(ipx) \quad ((5))$$

((5)) yields plane wave solutions with momentum related to \sqrt{E} . Thus, one sees quantum mechanics is strongly tied to the idea of plane wave solutions. Next, one may consider the case for which a potential exists.

Quantum Mechanics with a Potential

In classical statistical mechanics, the Boltzmann factor changes from $\exp(-p^2/(2mT))$ to $\exp(-(p^2+V)/(2mT))$.

What is the situation in quantum mechanics?

It has been argued that in quantum mechanics, a particle may be in a plane wave state $\exp(ipx)$ at any instant. This idea may be carried over to the case of a granular potential. Thus, it seems one does not really know the position of a particle as $\exp(ipx)$ holds for all x if one knows p . The potential may knock a particle from one p state into another, but there is no picture of a particle at x being accelerated from p_1 to p_2 as one moves to $x+dx$.

In the case of no potential, one considers the quantity $\sum_p f_p \exp(ipx)$, or the wavefunction $W(x)$. This vector describes the possible momentum states of the quantum particle with weights. In the case of a potential acting on $W(x)$, the result should again be a vector of the form $\sum_p b_p \exp(ipx)$, but with different weights as the basic scenario of a particle existing in one plane wave state or another does not change. If this is the case, one should be able to calculate the average overall energy for a plane wave $\exp(ipx)$. Unlike the case of no potential, it is not simply $p^2/2m$, but rather $p^2/2m + C_p$ where C_p represents the potential energy of the p wave. Then:

$$\sum_p \left(\frac{p^2}{2m} + C_p \right) f_p = E W \quad \text{where } W = \sum_p f_p \exp(ipx), \quad ((6))$$

Thus, if one may write C_p in terms of f_p , one would have an equation from which f_p could be determined. Again, f_p is determined solely through a plane wave averaging process, with no classical statistical mechanical counting of equal weight energy distribution vectors.

If one write $V(x)$ as a Fourier series $\sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$ one may try to combine this with $W(x)$ also written as a Fourier series. This might then yield C_p as:

$$C_p = \sum_k V_k f(p-k) \quad ((7))$$

It should also be noted that C_p must also equal $V(x)$ for an x such that $p^2/2m + V(x) = E$, which is the classical conservation equation. Thus, it is almost as if each plane wave equation ((6)) maps to a point x such that x and p satisfy classical conservation of energy.

Thus, it seems that if a quantum particle is in a p momentum state, even in a potential, it has a kinetic and potential energy which add to E , regardless of the p state. Again, there is not notion of acceleration from x_1 to x_2 as the p state $\exp(ipx)$ exists for all x . One has to ensure conservation of energy at the p level, with the total energy always being E . Thus, it is not only the quantum average kinetic energy plus the quantum average potential energy that equal E .

Can Classical Statistical Mechanics and Quantum Mechanics Coincide?

One may ask whether classical statistical mechanics and quantum mechanics ever coincide. Consider the bound state quantum equation:

$$-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W + V(x)W(x) = E W(x) \quad ((8))$$

In quantum mechanics, spatial density $d(x) = W(x)W(x)$ where W is real in the bound state.

For classical statistical mechanics, one may also find a spatial density by maximizing $-d(x)\ln(d(x))$ subject to a constraint. Let this constraint be $\int dx V(x)d(x) =$ average potential energy. Then one must maximize:

$-d(x)\ln(d(x)) + b \int dx V(x) d(x)$ by varying $d(x)$. This yields:

$$-\ln(d(x)) + (b-1)V(x) = 0 \quad ((9))$$

Consider ((8)) and imagine that $V(x) = c \ln(d(x))$. Divide ((8)) by $W(x)$ and it becomes identical to ((9)) where

$$E + 1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W / W = V(x)$$

Thus, it is possible to have quantum and classical statistical mechanics coincide, but only for $d(x) = c \ln(d(x))$ or :

$$W(x)W(x) = 2c \ln(W) \quad ((10))$$

This condition is satisfied for the ground state oscillator. One may inquire as to why the oscillator ground state allows for the classical statistical mechanical Boltzmann weight to satisfy the quantum condition. It may be noted that in quantum mechanics, the conditional probability factor used is $f_p \exp(ipx)$ which depends on p and x as it is linked to a momentum plane wave. If one could eliminate this coupling, the plane wave dependence would be gone, even though there would still be x dependence.

Consider the classical statistical probability function for p for an oscillator, namely $\exp(-ap^2)$. This term can combine with $\exp(ipx)$ to yield a Gaussian in a combined p, x variable i.e. $\exp(-a(p-ix/2a)^2)$. In one dimension, one may then change dp to $d(p-ix/2a)$. Thus, the idea of the plane wave seems to be removed for this example. In such

a case, one obtains the classical statistical mechanical picture to a certain degree. In other case, it seems the plane wave scenario persists.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have tried to argue that classical statistical mechanics and quantum mechanics (bound state) are both statistical theories, but are based on different conditions. Statistical mechanics seems to focus on the distribution of energy among particles (or time intervals). Quantum mechanics, on the other hand, is based on the idea that a particle, even in a potential, can be found in a plane wave momentum state at any instant. These states have weights of f_p , but when taking averages $f_p \exp(ipx)$ appears so it is as if one has a complex probability. Conservation of energy exists for each plane wave, but also for an overall average. The overall average must hold at each x point and it is this restriction which seems to dictate the form of f_p and not the classical statistical mechanical idea of distributing energy. For the ground state of an oscillator, however, it is possible to have an f_p which can incorporate $\exp(ipx)$ to form $f(p-ix/2a)$ which in a sense removes the plane wave picture. Alternatively, one may compare the Schrodinger equation for the ground state oscillator with the maxima equation for the quantity $-W^2 \ln(W) - b V(x) W W$ from classical statistical mechanics to see that the two are equal.